

Beamforming for Phased Array Antenna Using a Few-Mode Fiber

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Abstract: We experimentally demonstrate tunable optical beamforming for phased array antennas in a dispersion-engineered few-mode fiber that operates as a true-time delay line. The beam-pointing angle is steered continuously by changing the operational optical wave-length.

1. Introduction

Optical true-time delay line (TTDL) is the key component that allows for squint-free beamforming for phased array antennas (PAAs) over a wide frequency range [1]. A TTDL provides a set of evenly-spaced time-delayed versions of an input radiofrequency (RF) signal. Different techniques, including those based on dispersive fibers [2], fiber Bragg gratings [3] and multicore fibers [4], have been used to implement optical TTDLs. Moreover, we have recently proposed a tunable TTDL configuration implemented in a few-mode fiber (FMF), where the time delay among adjacent samples could be continuously tuned over a broad range by varying the optical wavelength [5]. Different spatial modes propagate in a FMF with different velocities due to their distinct group delays. Hence, at the FMF output, the modes provide different time-delayed replicas of an input signal. Through custom fiber design, the dispersion of the modes could be engineered such that the differential time delay $\Delta\tau$ between adjacent replicas is constant, leading to a FMF-based TTDL. Such a TTDL is particularly of interest for next-generation wireless communications systems, as it increases the versatility, capacity and compactness.

Recently, some true-time delay beamforming systems using a FMF have been demonstrated [6, 7]. However, in these studies, the FMF alone does not provide the TTDL operation and requires external delay control by either changing the fiber length [6] or using optical switches [7]. Here, we report, for the first time to our knowledge, the experimental demonstration of optical beamforming for PAA in a 1-km FMF link, where the FMF itself serves as a continuously tunable true-time delay line, providing the adequate time delay among the modes.

2. Experimental Setup and Results

We have developed a double-clad step-index few-mode fiber (Fig. 1(a)) [8], in which 5 of its spatial modes, namely, LP₀₁, LP₁₁, LP₂₁, LP₃₁ and LP₄₁, fulfill the conditions to operate as a continuously tunable TTDL; i.e., the differential group delays (DGDs) between any two neighboring modes, $\Delta\tau$, are (a) identical at a given wavelength and (b) vary linearly with the optical wavelength. The FMF was fabricated by YOFC company and its silica core, inner and outer claddings have radii of 9.1, 13 and 62.5 μm , with GeO₂ doping concentrations of 7.79 mol%, 5.93 mol%, and 0.22 mol%, respectively. Figure 1(b) shows the measured DGDs of the modes with respect to LP₀₁. The inset displays the average $\Delta\tau$ at each wavelength along with its corresponding standard deviation (error bars). As can be seen, $\Delta\tau$ increases linearly with the optical wavelength, confirming the suitability of the FMF to operate as a continuously tunable TTDL.

Fig. 1. (a) Refractive index profile of the fabricated FMF at 1550 nm, with the mode profile of the 5 modes suitable for TTDL operation. (b) DGDs of the modes with respect to LP₀₁, along with their average values (red dots) and corresponding error bars in the inset. (c) The 8-element phased array antenna. (d) Single antenna element radiation pattern, measured for 3 different individual elements.

An 8-element microstrip PAA with an element spacing of $d = 5.77$ mm ($\lambda_{RF}/2$ at 26 GHz) was designed and fabricated at our facilities (Fig. 1(c)). The measured radiation patterns of 3 representative antenna elements, displayed in Fig. 1(d), show considerable power variations and dissimilarities, indicating that our in-house built antenna is not ideal and has room for improvement. The developed FMF-based TTDL is used to implement a 5-element optical beamforming network for the PAA, using the setup of Fig. 2(a). The optical output of a tunable laser is intensity modulated by an RF signal at 26 GHz. The modulated signal is then amplified and launched into the 5 modes of interest (LP₀₁, LP₁₁, LP₂₁, LP₃₁ and LP₄₁) by a mode multiplexer fabricated by Cailabs. The worst-case average modal crosstalk for the mode multiplexer and demultiplexer pair, measured in back-to-back measurements, is -17.9 dB at 1530 nm. After demultiplexing the modes at the output of the 1-km FMF, the power of the signals are equalized using variable optical attenuators to have uniform power distribution. Then, the 5 optical signals are converted back to the electrical domain using individual photodiodes and after amplification, they are fed into the PAA, which is placed inside an anechoic chamber. A receiver horn antenna, placed 3 meters away from the transmitter antenna, is used to measure the received power. The optical wavelength is varied from 1543 to 1560 nm, corresponding to time delays between 65 and 94 ps. Consequently, the resulting beam-pointing angle, shown in Fig. 2(b), varies approximately from 22° down to -37°. The power variations in the radiation pattern of the antenna elements (Fig. 1(d)) affect the power and shape of the main and sidelobes. Thus, the results could be further improved by using a better PAA. Minor discrepancies on Δt among the modes could also lead to main lobe broadening and slight shift of the beam-pointing angle.

Fig. 2. (a) Experimental setup for optical true-time delay line beamformer in a PAA. PC: polarization controller, IM: intensity modulator, EDFA: erbium-doped fiber amplifier, MMUX (MDMUX): mode (de)multiplexer, VOA: variable optical attenuator, PD: photodetector, LNA: Low-noise amplifier. (b) Measured radiation patterns of the phased array antenna at different optical wavelengths.

3. Conclusions

We experimentally demonstrate continuously tunable optical beamforming for PPAs in a FMF link. The modes of the 1-km double-clad step-index FMF are dispersion-engineered to fulfill the requirements for tunable sampled TTDL operation. We measure the 5-element radiation pattern of a PPA in an anechoic chamber at an RF frequency of 26 GHz, and steer the beam-pointing angle within a 59° range, by just sweeping the optical wavelength of the laser.

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